

Deliverable D6 within 19ENG08

- Good Practice Guide on the calibration procedure for traceable electrical power measurement at the generator, converter and the filter using a reference power measurement system -

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Disclaimer

Any mention of commercial products within this report is for information only; it does not imply recommendation or endorsement by the partners in this project.

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1 Introduction

This good practice guide was generated in Work Package 3 (WP3) of the EMPIR project 19ENG08 “Traceable mechanical and electrical power measurement for efficiency determination of wind turbines” (WindEFCY). WP3 focused on traceable measurement of electrical power on wind turbine nacelle test benches.

This guide describes good practices for the calibration of the test bench electrical measurement instrumentation.

The calibration can be performed by connecting a previously calibrated reference power/energy measuring system in parallel with the test bench electrical measurement instrumentation. The reference system should have gone through component calibration, i.e., the voltage and current transducers are separately calibrated for current, voltage and power factor levels typical for the nacelle test bench. The calibration can then be performed using actual voltages and currents appearing during testing.

Alternatively, the test bench electrical measurement system components can be separately calibrated for voltage/current/power levels typical for the test setup.

The bandwidth requirements for the electrical power/energy measurement system vary a lot depending on the measurement. For measurements on electrical power network connection point, the voltages and currents are close to sinusoidal. However, the voltages and currents generated by variable frequency drives are far from sinusoidal and may contain frequency components up to hundreds of kilohertz.

1.1 Glossary

We have provided a glossary of technical terms that arise in the following description of the calibration of electrical power measurement in test benches using a reference power measurement system (RPMS).

1.2 Symbols and their meaning

Important symbols and their meaning regarding electrical power are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Symbols and their meaning.

Symbol	Unit	Meaning
P	W	Active power
U	V	Voltage
I	A	Current
Q	var	Reactive power
Q_{\sim}	var	Non-active power
S	VA	Apparent power
f	Hz	Frequency
λ		Power factor

2 Definition of the measurands for nacelle test bench

In order to determine the efficiency in a Nacelle Test Bench (NTB), the following measurands were defined. The electrical power measurement system shall be able to measure at least the following quantities:

- Active power,
- Power factor,
- Fundamental frequency,
- RMS current,
- RMS voltage, and
- Total Harmonic Distortion (THD).

In addition, the apparent power, reactive power, energy and the spectrum (harmonic content) can be measured.

The level of currents and voltages depend on the test bench. Each test bench has different measuring points where different current and voltage levels occur.

Figure 1: DyNaLab nacelle test bench at FhG IWES in Bremerhaven, Germany.

Figure 2: Typical test bench locations for electrical power measurement.

3 Electrical power definitions

The basic active electrical power¹ P definition is:

$$P = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T u(t) i(t) dt ,$$

where $u(t)$ and $i(t)$ are voltage and current respectively. The time interval T should ideally be chosen to be an integer multiple of the signal period.

3.1 IEC 60050 (IEV)

131-11-39: complex power, complex active power

under sinusoidal conditions, product of the phasor \underline{U} representing the voltage between the terminals of a linear two-terminal element or two-terminal circuit and the complex conjugate of the phasor \underline{I} representing the electric current in the element or circuit:

$$\underline{S} = \underline{U} \underline{I}^*$$

Note 1 to entry: Complex power is equal to $P + jQ$, where P is active power and Q is reactive power.

Note 2 to entry: The coherent SI unit for complex power is voltampere, VA.

131-11-41: apparent power

product of the rms voltage U between the terminals of a two-terminal element or two-terminal circuit and the rms electric current I in the element or circuit

$$S = UI$$

Note 1 to entry: Under sinusoidal conditions, the apparent power is the modulus of the complex power \underline{S} , thus $S = |\underline{S}|$.

Note 2 to entry: The coherent SI unit for apparent power is voltampere, VA.

131-11-42: active power

under periodic conditions, mean value, taken over one period T of the instantaneous power p

$$P = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T p dt$$

Note 1 to entry: Under sinusoidal conditions, the active power is the real part of the complex power \underline{S} , thus $P = \text{Re } \underline{S}$.

Note 2 to entry: The coherent SI unit for active power is watt, W.

¹ For simplification, this electrical power discussion is assuming a single-phase system. For three-phase formulas, see [1] and [2].

131-11-43: non-active power

for a two-terminal element or a two-terminal circuit under periodic conditions, quantity equal to the square root of the difference of the squares of the apparent power S and the active power P

$$Q_{\sim} = \sqrt{S^2 - P^2}$$

Note 1 to entry: Under sinusoidal conditions, the non-active power is the absolute value of the reactive power Q or the imaginary part of the complex power \underline{S} , thus $Q_{\sim} = |Q| = |\text{Im } \underline{S}|$.

Note 2 to entry: The coherent SI unit for non-active power is voltampere, VA. The special name "var" and its symbol "var" are also used. See 131-11-45.

131-11-44: reactive power

for a linear two-terminal element or two-terminal circuit, under sinusoidal conditions, quantity equal to the mean value of the product of the instantaneous voltage u and the instantaneous current i' which is equal to i but leading it by $\pi/2$:

$$Q = \overline{ui'} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T ui' dt,$$

where T denotes half the period of u , Q being equivalent to the product of the apparent power S and the sine of the displacement angle φ :

$$Q = S \sin \varphi.$$

Note 1 to entry: The reactive power is the imaginary part of the complex power \underline{S} , thus $Q = \text{Im } \underline{S}$. Its absolute value is equal to the non-active power, thus $|Q| = Q_{\sim}$.

Note 2 to entry: The coherent SI unit for reactive power is voltampere, VA. The special name var and its symbol var are also used.

131-11-46: power factor

under periodic conditions, ratio of the absolute value of the active power P to the apparent power S :

$$\lambda = \frac{|P|}{S}$$

Note – Under sinusoidal conditions, the power factor is the absolute value of the active factor.

131-11-49: active factor

for a two-terminal element or a two-terminal circuit under sinusoidal conditions, ratio of the active power to the apparent power

Note – The active factor is equal to the cosine of the displacement angle.

3.2 IEEE 1459-2010

IEEE 1459-2010 [1] defines electric power for sinusoidal and non-sinusoidal voltages and currents in balanced and unbalanced loading conditions. Active (P), reactive (Q) and apparent (S) power of a 3-phase system in each phase are respectively given by:

$$P = U_1 I_1 \cos \varphi_1 + \sum_{h \neq 1} U_h I_h \cos \varphi_h$$

$$Q = U_1 I_1 \sin \varphi_1 + \sum_{h \neq 1} U_h I_h \sin \varphi_h$$

$$S = UI$$

The definition is not limited to fundamental and harmonic components. If quantities U (voltage), I (current) and φ (phase angle) are received from Fourier series, the result will also include powers of intermodulation components as well as other spectral content in the voltage and current waveforms. More general expressions for active and reactive powers are:

$$P = \frac{1}{kT} \int_{\tau}^{\tau+kT} p(t) dt$$

$$Q = \frac{2\pi f}{kT} \int_{\tau}^{\tau+kT} i(t) \left[\int u(t) dt \right] dt$$

where $u(t)$ and $i(t)$ are instantaneous voltages and currents, f is the power system frequency and $T=1/f$.

3.3 DIN 40110-2002

Like IEEE 1459-2010 in the general case, DIN 40110-2002 [2] defines active power in a 3-phase system through integration in time domain. The active power is given by:

$$P = \frac{1}{kT} \int_{\tau}^{\tau+kT} u_{\mu 0}(t) i_{\mu p}(t) dt,$$

where $u_{\mu 0}(t)$ are the instantaneous phase voltages towards a virtual star ground and $i_{\mu p}(t)$ are instantaneous phase currents. Apparent and non-active power are given by:

$$S = U_{RMS} I_{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{kT} \int_{\tau}^{\tau+kT} u_{\mu 0}(t)^2 dt} \sqrt{\frac{1}{kT} \int_{\tau}^{\tau+kT} i_{\mu p}(t)^2 dt}$$

$$Q = \sqrt{S^2 - P^2}$$

3.4 ANSI C12

Drafting of ANSI C12.31 (for Electricity Meters – Measurement of AC Power, Energy and Power Factor) is under way, and once published, it will also provide a set of power definitions.

3.5 Non-harmonics

It should be noted that any spectral content, which has a period T_s such that $nT_s \neq kT$ will cause unavoidable error in the calculation. More discussion of this is in the next chapter concerning the sample clock. The IEEE standard mentions also that reactive power for non-sinusoidal conditions is not a trivial case and errors will be caused by the calculation.

3.6 Sampling basics

Digitizing a signal can be done by non-coherent or coherent sampling. Non-coherent sampling means that there is no relation between the frequency of the sampled signal and the sampling frequency. Since (for very practical reasons) we are limited to a finite number of samples for a finite amount of signal periods, some spectral leakage in Fourier analysis will inevitably occur. We would then have to choose

between simply selecting a sufficiently large number of samples before Fourier analysis or multiplying the sample vector with a window function. According to [3], the first method leads to long range spectral leakage and the second one, while reducing long range leakage, will create errors around the measurand frequency.

Another approach is coherent sampling. This method is often used in evaluating A/D converters and in AC metrology. In coherent sampling, there exists a relation between input signal frequency f_{in} and sample clock f_s [4] i.e., the sample rate is frequency locked to the measurand. If N_S is the sample vector length and N_{CYC} is an integer number of input signal cycles within the sample vector, the relation is

$$f_s = f_{in} \frac{N_S}{N_{CYC}}$$

Input frequency f_{in} is obviously fixed and from FFT analysis point of view it is convenient that N_S equals a power of two. With a predetermined vector length N_S , N_{CYC} is the only free variable in the equation. It can thus be considered an oversampling factor and according to [4], should be odd, preferably a prime number.

Sample clock frequency locking can be done either by locking directly to the measurand, like in [3] or by extracting signal frequency from digitized data and updating sample clock accordingly. The first method, while proven and robust, is not very flexible. For extracting signal frequency based on data, several methods are described in [5] and compared in [6]. Methods based on Fourier coefficients are generally computationally simple and can be adopted to track signals. They will also work well in non-sinusoidal situations. Quinn's interpolation method [7] estimates signal frequency based on three adjacent Fourier series elements, where the centre element is the Fourier series maximizer.

4 Typical reference power measuring system

Typical reference power measuring system is composed of a suitable multi-channel power analyser and wideband current and voltage sensors. The current and/or voltage sensors can be omitted, if the current and voltage levels are low enough for direct connection to the power analyser input. Optical isolators may also be needed to avoid interference due to ground currents. Some examples of typical commercial instruments are listed in Table 2. Figure 3 shows an example of instrumentation selected for measurement of power on medium voltage system with currents up to 2 kA.

Table 2: Typical reference power measuring system instruments

	Manufacturer	Type
Power analyser	ZES ZIMMER Yokogawa Fluke Norma	LMG 671 WT 5000 5000
Current sensor (zero flux principle)	Danisense LEM Hioki	DS200ID, DL2000ID, DR5000IM, etc IN series CT68XX, CT69XX
Voltage sensor (wideband divider)	ZES ZIMMER	HST series

Figure 3: Typical configuration of a reference electrical power measurement system.

4.1 Power analyser

4.1.1 Requirements for the power analyser

The recommended main requirements of the power analyser are listed in Table 3. The analyser has to be used with suitable sensors (see section 4.2.1). The relevant signals listed in section 2 are typically rich in harmonics and interharmonics. Therefore, the bandwidth of the power analyser should be larger than that of the sensors. The actual calibration of the power analyser is aimed at up to 5 kHz since the reference system should have a bandwidth of up to 5 kHz. To calibrate the power analyser, a suitable generator must be available. While each test bench has different measuring points requiring different sensors, their secondaries will be very similar. Therefore, the requirements for the power analyser do not depend on the measuring points. The calibration of the test bench system is performed at a fundamental frequency of 50 Hz. To determine the efficiency of a nacelle under test, a mechanical input power and an electrical output power is required. This electrical output power can be measured on the MV side of the MV transformer. The voltage occurring there is larger than 1 000 V, requiring the use of voltage sensors. Another possible measuring point would be on the LV side of the transformer. At this point the voltage is less than 1 000 V and can be measured directly with analyser, without sensors. At both points, the current exceeds the specifications of commercial power analysers; and sensors or transformers need to be used. A 230 V connection must be available in the test benches.

Table 3: Recommended main requirements for reference power analyser.

- Basic accuracy: 0.01%
- Bandwidth DC – 20 kHz
- Synchronization, e.g. 1PPS, PTP, internal timestamping
- Communication interface, e.g. Ethernet
- Inputs for mechanical measurement signals (e.g. torque or speed)

4.2 Current and voltage sensors

4.2.1 Requirements for current and voltage sensors

The relevant signals (Table 4) are rich in harmonics and interharmonics. Therefore, the reference sensors should have a 3 dB bandwidth of 20 kHz. The actual calibration of the individual sensors is aimed at up to 5 kHz since the RPMS should have a bandwidth of up to 5 kHz. To calibrate the reference sensors, a suitable generation must be available. Each test bench has different measuring points. Therefore, the requirements for the measurement sensors are different. The calibration of the EPMS in test benches is performed at a fundamental frequency of 50 Hz. To determine the efficiency of a nacelle under test, a mechanical input power and an electrical output power is required. This electrical output power can be measured on the MV side of the MV transformer. The voltage there is less than 20 kV and the current is less than 300 A. Another possible measuring point would be on the LV side of the transformer. At this point, the voltage is less than 1 000 V and the current is less than 3 000 A. In some test benches, it is not possible to measure on the secondary side because there is no space for measuring equipment. Some commercial sensors require an external power supply. A 230 V connection shall be available in the test benches.

Table 4: Overview of typical signals in nacelle test bench.

Signal	Sinusoidal distorted multi-level waveforms below 10 kHz	
LV side	< 700	V rms (1 000 V peak)
	< 2 000	A rms (3 000 A peak)
MV side	< 20 000	V phase to phase (12 kV phase to ground)
	< 300	A rms
Calibration frequency	50	Hz
Bandwidth reference current transformer	20 000	Hz (-3 dB bandwidth)
Bandwidth reference voltage divider	20 000	Hz (-3 dB bandwidth)
Bandwidth RPMS	5 000	Hz
Electrical supply voltage	230	V
Electrical interface	measuring lead (spring-loaded), D-SUB 9 pins	

4.2.2 Zero-flux current converters

Unlike Rogowski coils, zero-flux converters can be used for both AC and DC current measurements. A simplified schematic illustrating the zero-flux principle is shown in

Figure 4. Primary (measured) current I_p flows in a wire, causing a magnetic flux to be sensed by coils L_1 , L_2 and L_3 . The DC current is sensed with L_2 and L_3 . The coils are driven by an oscillator into saturation so that if zero DC current I_{pDC} flows in the primary conductor, both currents saturate at the same level. If I_{pDC} is no-zero the resulting difference in the saturation currents, which is proportional to I_{pDC} , can be sensed. The AC part is sensed by L_1 , which operates as a normal current transformer similarly to a Rogowski coil (although L_1 is not air-cored). The DC and AC part are then amplified by an integrator, which drives a scaled current I_s into L_4 . This current will balance the flux created by I_p and is in turn converted into voltage by burden resistor R_B . A precision sense amplifier then produces a full-swing output voltage, which can be measured. At some frequency the control loop, which balances the fluxes will no longer operate properly due to phase lag between input and output (it needs to stay in inversion for the loop to work). Beyond this frequency the converter will function as a passive current transformer and I_s will hold higher current components than what are actually driven by the power amplifier. The bandwidth is limited only by stray capacitances in the structure and non-idealities in the burden resistor.

Figure 4: Zero-flux current converter operating principle

4.2.3 Compressed gas capacitor based divider

Compressed gas capacitor (Figure 5) based dividers have some advantages from measurement accuracy point of view. Their voltage and temperature dependencies are extremely low, and they have wide and flat bandwidth. Also, they do not suffer from proximity effect, which is typical for high voltage dividers with open structure.

They cannot be used for measurement of DC. They are widely used in high voltage testing but are typically not approved for connection to the power network.

Figure 5: Compressed gas high voltage capacitor.

- 1 – HV electrode,
- 2 – LV electrode,
- 3 – support,
- 4 – Insulating tube,
- 5 – LV electrode connector

4.2.4 Voltage transformer

Traditional voltage transformers also have some good characteristics from measurement accuracy point of view. Their voltage and temperature dependencies are extremely low. They do not suffer from proximity effect, which is typical for high voltage dividers with open structure.

They cannot be used for measurement of DC, and their bandwidth is typically too low for measurement signals containing harmonics.

4.2.5 Universal voltage divider

Wideband voltage sensors are typically used, when a flat bandwidth from DC up to even MHz range is needed. The schematic diagram of a typical universal divider (also called RCR divider) is shown in Figure 6. Note that the cable capacitance and measuring instrument input resistance are in the equations for flat frequency response matching.

Figure 6: Typical configuration of a universal (RCR) divider.
 The equations for flat frequency response are shown on top right corner.
 R_D can be omitted if measured frequencies stay below 100 kHz.

5 Performing a calibration

Requirements for the calibration differ according to the waveform to be measured. Voltage and current from frequency converters typically have significant harmonic content, and wideband calibration of all measuring system components is recommended. When the voltage and current waveforms do not contain significant harmonics, calibration using 50 Hz signals only may be sufficient.

Voltage sensor calibration is typically valid only for the setup used in calibration.

Especially when a set-up is directly connected to the public electricity grid, safety requirements such as over-voltage need to be considered carefully.

To determine the electrical power for the efficiency of wind turbines in the nacelle test bench, a calibrated reference power/energy measurement system must be available. For cost and time reasons, commercial measurement technology is used, making verification of the interconnected system unavoidable.

In most cases, the manufacturer's specifications are sufficient for commercial use. For more specialized applications, such as measurement campaigns on wind turbines, there are some aspects that need to be investigated in more detail. One such aspect is the long-term stability of a sensor. Since there is not just one operating point in a nacelle test bench, but the test bench moves to different operating points, and both short-term and long-term measurements are made at the different operating points, the behavior of the measurement technology must also be investigated and calibrated to meet these requirements.

For a well-defined purpose, the calibration can be optimized to exclude or reconstruct and account for non-normal influencing variables to achieve a higher measurement accuracy with lower uncertainties than specified by the manufacturer.

A calibration can be performed for individual components as well as for the entire measurement chain. A measurement chain calibration reflects the total uncertainty of a system, considering also e.g. the

influence of the environment, the setup including wiring, temperature dependency and EMC sensitivity, which in practice may differ from the calculated total uncertainty of the individual components.

With a calibrated reference measurement system (RPMS), the embedded measurement technology (EPMS) of the operators of nacelle test benches can be calibrated in two ways. A calibration of the built-in measurement system can be performed on-site, or the measurement technology can be removed by the operators and sent to a metrology institute such as METAS, VTT or PTB. If the calibration is not carried out on site, but e.g., at a metrology institute the calibration shall be carried out with typically occurring defined current, voltage and power factor values and the required bandwidth.

Table 5. Advantages and disadvantages of on-site calibration

Advantages	Disadvantages
+ Calibration under on-site conditions, such as structure, EMC, temperature, vibration	- Loss of manpower in the event of a delay in the measurement campaign (more difficult to arrange appointments with the metrology institute)
+ No risk of damage to the systems during removal and transport	- There must be enough space for the reference measurement equipment (places are often difficult to access and narrow).
+ Time and cost savings through disassembly and shipping of the measurement technology	- Extensive planning of the installation of the reference measuring system required (mechanical mounting, EMC, sources of interference)
+ Calibration changes of individually adapted measuring points (current/voltage changes) possible	- Finding a suitable reference measuring system that can be transported robustly and flexibly
+ Identify sources of error and sub-optimal configurations, such as interference from adjacent sensors, which can be reduced in the field.	- Changing the behavior of the RPMS under on-site conditions
	- Risk of errors due to time pressure during ongoing measurements

Table 6. Advantages and disadvantages of external calibration

Advantages	Disadvantages
+ Use of standardised procedures and structures	- Measuring equipment to be calibrated must be removed and shipped by the test bench operator
+ Simplified scheduling for calibration, which can also take place after the measurement campaign without time pressure	- High effort for change/extension of a performed calibration (after return)
+ Controlled environment	- High effort to simulate on-site conditions as closely as possible in the laboratory
+ High precision equipment	- On-site conditions cannot be ideally replicated
+ Simple modification of individual measurement requirements	
+ Direct evaluation of data (no data loss)	

What needs to be determined for an RPMS:

- Voltage sensors

- Voltage dividers: HST12 is stable (negligible self-heating), if operated at 6kV (50 ppm with a total uncertainty of 300 ppm, rectangular distribution))
- Voltage dividers: For voltages from 6 kV to 21 kV, a total uncertainty of 1000 ppm (rectangular distribution) is to be assumed for HST12 due to self-heating.
- Voltage dividers: proximity effect.
- Calibration on nominal voltage(s)
 - Ratio error
 - Phase placement
- Frequency response up to 20 kHz
- Repeatability
- Voltage sensor must be type tested or have suitable overvoltage protection
- Current sensors
 - Linearity
 - Influence of neighbouring sensors and current conductors
 - Effect of cable routing (centre forward conductor, distance between return conductors)
 - Repeatability
 - Calibration (at least) on three currents (min, middle, max)
 - Ratio error
 - Phase placement
 - Frequency response up to 20 kHz
 - Amount error
- Power analyser
 - Power definitions used by the analyser
 - Crosstalk between the channels
 - Linearity
 - Frequency response up to 20 kHz
 - Use of correct filter settings
 - Synchronisation possibilities

5.1 Example of voltage sensor calibration

The importance of calibration is illustrated by the example of the 3-phase voltage transfer standard (ZES ZIMMER HST12-3). The data sheet of the HST12-3 specifies maximum $\pm 0.05\%$ (500 ppm) ratio error deviation from nominal and a maximum phase displacement of $\pm 0.06^\circ$ (1050 μrad) at 50 Hz. Figure 7 shows results of a long-term test of the voltage divider. The voltage was varied from 2.4 kV to 12 kV (phase to ground voltage). The measurement deviations were documented, the divider was switched on and off frequently and operated over a longer period of time and the behaviour was observed.

The results show that the specification for the dividing ratio of ± 500 ppm is only valid for long-term measurements at a level lower than 6 kV. At a higher level of e.g. 12 kV, the specification is only valid for short-term measurements less than 30 min. If the divider is switched on several times in succession at 12 kV and operated for longer than 30 min, the dividing ratio shows a drift of up to 700 ppm, so that a higher uncertainty of 1000 ppm must be assumed.

The measured maximum phase displacement was within $\pm 500 \mu\text{rad}$, which is within $\pm 1000 \mu\text{rad}$ specification.

Figure 7: Measured dividing ratio error (top) and phase displacement (bottom) of a HST12-3 channel.

6 Measurement uncertainty determination

Model equation, GUM & GUM workbench

Yokogawa uncertainty calculator:

<https://tmi.yokogawa.com/pt/library/resources/faqs/power-analyzer-accuracy-and-basic-uncertainty-calculator/>

Clause 1.4.2 from 15RPT04 TracePQM – GUIDE:

1.4.2 Example (GUF) - Uncertainty evaluation for the DSWM

The following example shows the main terms to take into account for the uncertainty evaluation of the active power in low frequency domain using the DSWM under sinusoidal steady state. The uncertainty is evaluated using GUF.

- Let's recall that in sinusoidal mode, the active power P is defined by the relation:

$$P = U \cdot I \cdot \cos(\phi) \quad (1.12)$$

where U and I are respectively the voltage and the current of the signals $u(t)$ and $i(t)$, and ϕ represents their phase shift. The quantities U , I and ϕ are independent.

- By applying the law of propagation of the uncertainties to the relation 1.12, appears an expression with terms of uncertainties in phase and in quadrature:

$$\left(\frac{u(P)}{P}\right)^2 = \overbrace{\left(\frac{u(U)}{U}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u(I)}{I}\right)^2}^{\text{uncertainties in phase}} + \overbrace{\tan^2\phi \cdot u^2(\phi)}^{\text{uncertainties in quadrature}} \quad (1.13)$$

- The quadrature uncertainty terms have a zero contribution on the global balance for $\phi = 0^\circ$ and a contribution that tends towards infinity when ϕ tends to 90° . The relative uncertainty will therefore always be expressed as a function of the apparent power $S = I \cdot U$ in the form:

$$\left(\frac{u(P)}{P}\right)^2 = \left[\left(\frac{u(U)}{U}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u(I)}{I}\right)^2 \right] \cdot \cos^2\phi + \sin^2\phi \cdot u^2(\phi) \quad (1.14)$$

- The voltage U is brought back, by means of a voltage divider of ratio k , to a level of voltage u_1 which can be measured on the 1 V range:

$$U = k \cdot u_1 \quad (1.15)$$

The term $\frac{u(U)}{U}$ is:

$$\left(\frac{u(U)}{U}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{u(u_1)}{u_1}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u(k)}{k}\right)^2 \quad (1.16)$$

- The current I is measured via a shunt of impedance Z :

$$I = \frac{u_2}{|Z|} \text{ with } |Z| = \frac{R}{1 + \delta} \quad (1.17)$$

where $|Z|$ is the module of the impedance of the shunt, R is the value of its DC resistance and δ is its AC/DC transfer difference.

The term $\frac{u(I)}{I}$ is:

$$\left(\frac{u(I)}{I}\right)^2 = \left[\left(\frac{u(R)}{R}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u(\delta)}{1 + \delta}\right)^2 \right] + \left(\frac{u(u_2)}{u_2}\right)^2 \quad (1.18)$$

6. In equations 1.16 and 1.18, u_1 and u_2 are measured voltages by the two DMMs in DCV mode. They are affected by errors due to DMM bandwidth limitation ε_{BP} , integration time ε_{Ta} , signal quantization ε_Q , and sampling jitter ε_J :

$$u_{1,2} = u_{DCV} \cdot \left(1 + \varepsilon_{BP} + \varepsilon_{Ta} + \varepsilon_Q + \varepsilon_J\right) \quad (1.19)$$

The terms $\frac{u(u_1)}{u_1}$ and $\frac{u(u_2)}{u_2}$ are:

$$\left(\frac{u(u_{1,2})}{u_{1,2}}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{u(u_{DCV})}{u_{DCV}}\right)^2 + \frac{u^2(\varepsilon_{BP}) + u^2(\varepsilon_{Ta}) + u^2(\varepsilon_Q) + u^2(\varepsilon_J)}{1 + \varepsilon_{BP} + \varepsilon_{Ta} + \varepsilon_Q + \varepsilon_J} \quad (1.20)$$

7. Finally, the last parameter to be analyzed is the phase shift ϕ between the voltage $u(t)$ and the current $i(t)$. The different sources of phase shift are the voltage divider ϕ_{VD} , the current shunt ϕ_{Shunt} and the DMMs. The DMMs can phase out the signals due to their bandwidth difference ϕ_{BP} , their integration time ϕ_{Ta} , their tripping delay ϕ_r , and their sampling jitter ϕ_J . To all these sources of error is added the phase shift ϕ_Q due to the quantization of the signals. We finally have:

$$\phi = \phi_0 + \phi_{VD} + \phi_{Shunt} + \left[\phi_{BP} + \phi_{Ta} + \phi_r + \phi_J\right] + \phi_Q \quad (1.21)$$

The term $u(\phi)$ is:

$$u^2(\phi) = u^2(\phi_0) + u^2(\phi_{VD}) + u^2(\phi_{Shunt}) + \left[u^2(\phi_{BP}) + u^2(\phi_{Ta}) + u^2(\phi_r) + u^2(\phi_J)\right] + u^2(\phi_Q) \quad (1.22)$$

8. Additionally to this, following terms can be take into account:

- Current shunt's DC resistance, AC/DC transfer difference and phase shift drift
- Voltage divider's ratio and phase shift drift
- DMMs resolution for voltage and current measurements

All individual error terms and their associated uncertainties should be evaluated experimentally and/or by calculation. Below Table 1.7 summarize the uncertainty estimation for active power calculation with the three independent terms described above.

Uncertainty evaluation for active power P in W/VA				
Main uncertainty components	Type method of evaluation	Standard uncertainty value $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity coefficient C_i	Standard uncertainty $u_i = C_i u(x_i)$
Voltage $\frac{u(U)}{U}$	Here specify the type A or B of all sub uncertainty components	Here specify the value of all sub uncertainty components	$\cos(\phi)$	Root square sum of all sub uncertainty components value and sensibility coefficient (in V/V)
Current $\frac{u(I)}{I}$	Here specify the type A or B of all sub uncertainty components	Here specify the value of all sub uncertainty components	$\cos(\phi)$	Root square sum of all sub uncertainty components value and sensibility coefficient (in A/A)
Phase shift $u(\phi)$	Here specify the type A or B of all sub uncertainty components	Here specify the value of all sub uncertainty components	1	Root square sum of all sub uncertainty components value and sensibility coefficient (in rad)
<p>The standard uncertainty for active power P in W/VA is the root square sum of the standard uncertainty of the three independent components: 1) Voltage $\frac{u(U)}{U}$; 2) Current $\frac{u(I)}{I}$; 3) Phase shift $u(\phi)$</p>				
<p>Expanded uncertainty for active power P in W/VA is equal to standard uncertainty multiplied by 2 which gives 95.45 % coverage factor</p>				

Table 1.7: Summary of uncertainty evaluation of active power in W/VA

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8 Acronyms

AC	alternating current
DAQ	data acquisition
DC	direct current
DUT	device under test
EMPIR	European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research
EPMS	electrical power measurement system
EU	European Union
LV	low voltage
MV	medium voltage
NTB	nacelle system test bench
NTP	network time protocol
PTB	Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt
RPMS	reference power measurement system
THD	total harmonic distortion
VTT	Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd.

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